

STIMULI RESPONSE, STRUCTURAL RECONFIGURATION, AND PROPERTY CONTROL IN CROSS-LINKED POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

Structural developments in epoxy-based materials systems, subject to chemical and mechanical stimuli, have been investigated using a combination of experimental and computational techniques. Concurrent Raman and Brillouin scattering is used to monitor the formation of epoxy networks over time, both in terms of the structural connectivity of the network and the evolution of chemical bonding configurations. The elastic modulus of epoxy cured with an amine hardener comprises two contributions: one directly related to the concentration of covalent bonds that form and another one due to non-bonding interactions that arise as the network relaxes into an optimally packed configuration. Complementary information is provided by molecular models of epoxy systems generated using reactive molecular dynamics simulations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins are commonly used in many industrial applications, particularly as adhesives, protective coatings, and as the matrix material for fiber-reinforced composites. Depending on the application, a variety of different blends of resins and hardeners and different processing environments (temperature, pressure, etc.) are required to ensure optimal material characteristics.¹⁻⁵ Thermal history, chemical composition, and interfacial effects can all influence the cure behavior of the epoxy, and result in changes in the final chemical and mechanical properties of the cured resin.⁶⁻⁸ Therefore, it is critical to understand the connection between the processing conditions and the final material properties of the resin in order to ensure optimal performance of the resin in its application.

Ideally, these properties should be measurable *in-situ* so that the manufacturing process can be monitored in real time for quality assurance. However, common methods used to determine the cure kinetics and evolution of mechanical properties include differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and mechanical viscometry.⁹⁻¹¹ Both of these are invasive measurement techniques, and cannot be used to monitor cure *in-situ* under normal manufacturing conditions. In contrast, here we describe a light scattering technique that allows us to measure visco-elastic properties detailed chemical characteristics *in-situ* and without mechanical contact to the sample: concurrent Brillouin and Raman light scattering. Raman light scattering (RLS) measurements allow one to monitor the cure process of epoxy resins. These resins have many active Raman modes, some of which remain constant during reaction and can be used to normalize spectra and others that change as a result of cure reactions and can be used to monitor polymerization and cross-linking processes that underlie network formation.¹²⁻¹⁴ Meanwhile, Brillouin light scattering (BLS) is an invaluable tool in the analysis of network formation, because it is a non-destructive micro-scale probe of the interconnectedness of network components.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ Combining both methods makes it possible to relate the evolution of mechanical properties with the underlying chemical processes that drive polymer network formation.¹⁸

This paper provides an account of three findings, which together shine new light on the structural developments in cross-linked polymers that undergo reactions subject to the confinement imposed by the presence of an interface. First we determined that the elastic modulus of epoxy varies depending on whether the region probed is densely packed with reinforcing fibers or not. Exploring possible reasons for why this may be the case, we studied the evolution of the elastic modulus as a function of the degree of cure, varying the cure rate by means of the temperature or the resin-to-hardener ratio.

Finally, to examine whether the proximity of interfaces may impose geometric hindrances onto the completion of cross-linking reactions, we studied the epoxy network development using reactive molecular dynamics simulations.

2 PROCEDURAL DETAILS

2.1 Sample preparation

For the first aspect of the investigation we used a composite system consisting of eight layers of 45° braided carbon fibers embedded in a matrix of epoxy resin. The resin used is Epon 862, which was hardened with Epikure 9553, both manufactured by Hexion Specialty Chemicals. The average fiber diameter in our samples is 6 μm . Cubic samples were cut from the composite and mounted for polishing such that the axial tows lay parallel to the polishing plane. The sample was then polished using progressively finer compounds, ending with 0.25 μm SiC. The result of the polishing is a sample surface that appears smooth at 100x magnification on our microscope. For comparison, we also prepared bulk epoxy samples that were cut and polished in the same manner as the composite samples.

The epoxy system used for this study is composed of Epon 862 resin (Diglycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F, Hexion Specialty Chemicals) mixed with Epikure 9553 amine hardener (proprietary formulation, Hexion Specialty Chemicals). When varying the ratio of resin to hardener, all measurements are carried out at the fixed temperature of 40°C. To prepare each sample for the light scattering measurements, resin and hardener are added to a glass vial such that the desired concentrations of amine and epoxide are available for reaction. The components are mixed by hand for one minute at room temperature. The mixture is then allowed to stand for an additional minute to allow any trapped gas bubbles that formed during the mixing process to escape. Next, the sample is injected into a sample holder composed of a perforated spacer separating two glass coverslips. The sample fills a circular aperture with a 20 mm diameter and 2 mm thickness. Finally, the sample holder containing the epoxy is placed in a heating cell on the optical table, which has been pre-heated to the desired reaction temperature. The temperature of the heating cell is monitored using a thermocouple placed less than a millimeter from the sample holder window. The heating cell temperature is controlled using a Eurotherm PID controller. The heating cell is mounted on the optical table such that the center of the sample is positioned in the path of the 532 nm probing laser (Coherent Verdi) and at the focal point of the spectrometer collection optics. The laser power at the sample is 85 mW for all measurements.

2.2 Concurrent Raman and Brillouin light scattering

Raman (RLS) and Brillouin light scattering (BLS) are similar spectroscopic techniques. Both are inelastic light scattering methods, which measure the shift in energy of scattered light from its incident energy. Both techniques require the sample to be irradiated with monochromatic laser light, and the scattered light to be collected using collimating optics. Once the scattered light is collimated, it can easily be directed to a spectrometer for measurement. Our experimental setup takes advantage of this ability to direct the collimated light, by placing a rotating mirror between the collection lens and the spectrometers. By rotating this mirror we direct the scattered light into either the Raman spectrometer or Brillouin spectrometer. In this manner, we can attribute measurements from both instruments to the same 50 μm diameter scattering volume. As a result, we can precisely relate the evolving visco-elastic properties of the sample to its chemical state. The combined RLS and BLS spectra collection takes of the order of two minutes, while the duration of the curing is about three hours.

Between absorption and emission, the light may couple to vibronic excitations that reflect the change in electronic polarizability in chemical bonds subject to thermal vibrations. This affects the spectrum of the scattered light in a manner that allows one to identify the type and concentration of certain molecular building blocks, which is the mechanism underlying Raman spectroscopy. To monitor the degree of cure in epoxy we normalized all Raman spectra with respect to the 1053 cm^{-1} peak, attributed to the phenol rings of the resin, which remain at a constant concentration throughout the cure process. As the epoxide and amine groups react the epoxide rings open, which results in a decrease of the 1275 cm^{-1} peak intensity. Comparing the ratio of the 1275 cm^{-1} peak intensity with

that of the 1053 cm⁻¹ phenol peak allows us to determine the degree of cure. For our analysis, we used a Princeton Instruments TriVista triple monochromator with Princeton Instruments Spec-10 liquid nitrogen cooled CCD detector. All spectra are centered at 1275 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the breathing mode of the epoxide ring.¹⁹⁻²¹

For BLS measurements, we analyze light that scatters from periodic density waves associated with thermally excited phonons in the sample. The frequency of the scattered light is Doppler-shifted from that of the incident light by an amount ω_b . This shift is related to the speed of sound in the scattering medium, c_L , by the relation $\omega_b = qc$, where q is the wavevector of the scattering phonon, and the subscript associated with the velocity denotes the mode of elastic deformation. The wavevector magnitude can be determined based on the scattering angle, and the sound velocity can be related to the longitudinal modulus M' using $M' = \rho c$, where ρ is the density of the material. Note that the moduli determined using BLS correspond to the adiabatic elastic constants, i.e., that do not account for strain relaxation of a material under load, but rather correspond to the elastic response of a structure in thermodynamic equilibrium. Using BLS we can detect shear (S) and longitudinal (L) wave modes, though the particular modes observed depend upon the scattering geometry. A detailed description of the measurement method, the underlying principles, and the formalisms used for the data analysis is given in our earlier papers and the pertinent literature.²²⁻²⁴ Brillouin spectra were recorded using a Sandercock tandem Fabry-Perot interferometer (TFPI). The mirror spacing used was 5 mm and the scanning range was 200 nm over 512 channels for greater collection speeds.

2.3 Reactive molecular dynamics simulations

We simulate all pertinent aspects of the epoxy cure reactions that lead to network formation and relaxation, and thereby generate realistic models of cross-linked epoxy structures. To this end we use a heuristic bond formation approach that combines molecular dynamics (MD) and Monte Carlo (MC) simulation techniques. In short, a system of resin and hardener molecules is relaxed at finite temperature, typically between room temperature and 500 K, using MD simulations. The configuration is periodically examined for the proximity between reactive sites, and bonds assigned if the reaction partners are close within a certain cut-off distance. The configuration is then relaxed towards the nearest energy minimum using a conjugated gradient descent. If the system energy is lowered in this process, the bonds are kept, and if not, the bonds are rejected with a certain probability. Subsequently, the system is thermalized again and allowed to explore phase space at finite temperature and establish new reactive encounters. This procedure is repeated until degrees of cure of the order of 70-80% are reached. As the degree of cure increases, the reactivity slows down significantly, and eventually, the time between successful encounters exceeds a reasonable duration for the simulation run.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Modulus mapping of a composite cross-section

The composite system we chose for our modulus mapping study consists of eight layers of 45° braided carbon fibers embedded in a matrix of epoxy resin. The resin used is Epon 862, which was hardened with Epikure 9553, both manufactured by Hexion Specialty Chemicals. The average fiber diameter in our samples is 6 μm. Cubic samples were cut from the composite and mounted for polishing such that the axial tows lay parallel to the polishing plane. The sample was then polished using progressively finer compounds, ending with 0.25 μm SiC. The result of the polishing is a sample surface that appears smooth at 100x magnification on our microscope. For comparison, we also prepared bulk epoxy samples that were cut and polished in the same manner as the composite samples.

Figure 1: (a) Illustration of the windowing function centered at the measurement point, used to determine local fiber density; fibers are counted with a weight given by the windowing function magnitude at the location of the fiber center. (b) Map of the longitudinal elastic modulus as a function of the location within a fiber tow.

We carried out about 400 BLS measurements at different positions within the epoxy phase on the polished surface and also determined the distance between the measurement spot and the nearest fiber surface, as well as that to all the surrounding fiber centers. Our analysis shows that the distance to the nearest surface is a relatively unreliable measure, whereas the distance to all fiber centers allows us to evaluate a local fiber density using a Gaussian windowing function, as illustrated in Figure 1a. The modulus decreases linearly as a function of this local fiber density.²⁴ The overall change in the modulus between epoxy regions devoid of fibers and those most densely packed with fibers is about 4.5%. This does not seem very significant from a mechanical property point of view. However, to achieve such a change in modulus as a result of residual stresses would require an estimated strain of three times the failure strain. Residual stress was also ruled out as the reason based on Raman spectral analysis.²⁴ It is therefore likely that significant structural and/or chemical changes exist in the polymer as a function of the fiber packing density. These variations in polymer characteristics must be the result of the conditions during cure.

3.2 Modulus mapping as a function of the degree of cure

We investigated two possible causes that could lead to a different modulus in regions densely packed with fibers as opposed to regions devoid of fibers: the cure temperature and the stoichiometry of the resin-hardener mixture. The rationale for this is based on the consideration that carbon fibers have a higher thermal conductivity than the resin-hardener mixture, especially when it is still a viscous fluid. Hence, the rate of cure could be faster away from fibers due to local heating as the result of the exothermic cross-linking reaction. Furthermore, Epon 862 and Epikure 9553 in the unreacted liquid state are not very miscible,^{25,26} and it is possible that the presence of the graphite surface catalyzes the separation of the two components or that a porous graphite surface simply absorbs the smaller-sized hardener molecules.

Since we determine the Raman and Brillouin spectra of light scattered from the same scattering volume in the samples and at the same time, we can directly relate the elastic properties to the degree of cure. These results are shown in Figure 2. The detailed analysis has been reported in an earlier publication,²³ so that we limit our discussion here to the most salient points. Overall, we find that for slow reactions, i.e., at low temperatures and for compositions that exhibit a lack of hardener, the modulus changes almost linearly with the degree of cure. The faster the reaction, i.e., with increasing temperatures and increasing hardener concentrations, the modulus vs. degree of cure relationship curbs

downward. In other words for an intermediate degree of cure, say 40%, the modulus of a rapidly reacted system lags behind that of a slowly reacted system; the latter can in some cases be almost twice that of the former. Ultimately, for systems that reach full cure of about 80%, the moduli become again independent of the reaction rate.

Figure 2: Longitudinal elastic modulus as a function of the degree of cure for (a) systems reacted at different temperatures, and (b) for systems reacted with different hardener-to-epoxy molar ratios.

3.3 Effect of confinement

Our simulations of alkane polymers near metal substrates show that the presence of the interface can have far reaching consequences in terms of local changes in elastic properties, to the extent that the modulus is strongly affected at distances from the interface where no structural changes are apparent. Using simulations we cannot yet reach system sizes commensurate to the spatial resolution afforded by micro-Brillouin scattering. However, our simulation results, despite the disparity in length scales, still allow us to draw some conclusions with regard to the effect of spatial confinement on the degree of cure near the interfaces.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the degree of cure at different times during the curing process.

To this effect, we carried epoxy cure simulations near a graphite surface within an epoxy film of about 150 Å thickness. Figure 3 shows the degree of cure as a function of the distance from the substrate surface at various times during the simulation. While we observe significant local fluctuations, these do not seem to be correlated with the spatial coordinate. Except perhaps for the first 15 Å adjacent to the interface, the cure appears to advance stochastically but homogeneously. From these simulations we thus infer that, if the presence of an interface does not interfere with the polymerization and cross-linking reactions at a distance a few tens of Angstroms away from an interface, it is unlikely that geometrical constraints interfere with the network formation micrometers away from the substrate surface.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Post cure analysis of the elastic properties of epoxy in the space between fibers shows that the modulus is about 4.5% lower than in bulk epoxy. Based on the magnitude of this change and on Raman spectroscopic analysis, we can rule out that this property change is due to residual stress. Atomistic simulations also suggest that the origin is not spatial confinement. However, a systematic study of the epoxy cure kinetics reveals that the cure rate, whether affected by the reaction temperature or by the stoichiometry of the resin-hardener mixture, has a significant effect on the structural developments in the epoxy. Our observations are consistent with a 12% depletion of the hardener within the interfacial region, most likely due to a physical or chemical affinity between hardener and graphite surface.

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